

A method of 3D GUI design for SCADA using Unity

Kum-Thap Jang¹, Kyong-Mi Kim¹, Song-Hyon Kim¹, Kum-Song Ri*

¹Faculty of Mechanical Science and Technology, Kim Cheak University of Technology, Kyogudong No.60, Yonggwang street, Pyongyang 950003, Democratic People's Republic of Korea

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*Correspondence:

Kum-Song Ri

Faculty of Mechanical Science
and Technology, Kim Cheak
University of Technology,
Kyogudong No.60, Yonggwang
street, Pyongyang 950003,
Democratic People's Republic
of Korea

Email: rks90531@star-co.net.kp

Abstract

With the recent advancement of science and technology, the large-scale SCADA system 2D GUI of large-scale production processes has been designed with more intuitive and efficient 3D GUI. This paper presents a method to design 3D GUI for SCADA of a process control system composed of PLC with Unity software for various applications including game development. That is, in a production process automation system, the information from the PLC deployed on site is database-based on the control room computer and this database is connected to the 3D GUI created by Unity to construct the SCADA system. The 3D GUI design for SCADA by Unity, which also meets ergonomic requirements, is very effective in the field of systems where the amount of data to be displayed on the interface is large and the complexity and detail must be represented. Then, we demonstrate the advantages of the 3D interface introduced by this method through user experiments.

Keywords: SCADA, unity, 3D GUI, PLC

Introduction

As everything is integrated and AI-enabled by information devices, including computers, real-time data processing is increasing.

As the production processes are integrated and expanded, a high-performance computer for big data processing is required.

However, with the rapid development of computer manufacturing, high-performance computers, which were not used at high prices in the past, have become popular among people because of their low cost.

This has provided the possibility to switch from SCADA systems that rely on 2D GUIs to 3D GUIs with higher visual and effective performance in the field of interface design in the process area where big data are processed.

The SCADA support program, including WinCC, Adroit and Lview, has a drawback in monitoring and data processing because 2D GUI is effective in low data throughput systems, but limited in large systems to reflect large amounts of data on interfaces [1]. To overcome this, the use of 3D graphics to visualize large amounts of data has been investigated [1-4].

There are many approaches to generate 3D models in 2D models, including methods to generate 3D models using GIS information [7,8] and methods to generate 3D models based on 2D graphics [9,10].

The methods of writing 3D graphics without code have been described, but their visualization has been improved [16]. The use of custom software, standard database libraries for program safety has been demonstrated [1]. We have developed a method to design an interface by using Unity software that supports both Graphics and User Interface functionality, and then connect it with a PLC program installed in the field to design 3D GUI for SCADA of process control systems.

Visualization in Unity-written interfaces, unlike the simple switching functions of the previous, can provide a high visual impact that allows a very delicate change to be designed visually and vividly, due to the programming personality.

Figure 7 shows that the higher the temperature of the filament in Unity, the more color of the filament changes and the corresponding current is amplified.

The Unity software allows the implementation of a high-efficiency, transparent, and effective, physical and chemical phenomenon in space, which can maximize the convenience, stability and reliability of monitoring.

Design method

In this paper, the SCADA design of a heat-treatment process automation system is considered as a challenge for 3D GUI design using Unity software. To build a SCADA system, an application with GUI functionality, database functionality, and an OPC (OLE for Process Control) server for collecting data from physical inputs and outputs are required.

We used Unity as an application to implement GUI functionality, Microsoft Access as a database, and Kepware server as an OPC server, and Fatek PLC as a physical input and output.

Automatic control system of heat treatment process(Fig.1).

Fig. 1. Automatic control system flow diagram of heat treatment process.

GUI design Unity has powerful Graphics and UI functions, so GUI functionality implementation is not a problem. We have built a 3D model of the process plant with a 3D max or Bs SolidWorks application and imported it into Unity. The extension is *.fbx.

Fig 2. SCADA Design Architecture with Unity

We transfer to the Database System (database system) through Physical Interface (OPC interface) at physical I/O(Fig. 2).

The database system that receives data transfers data to Unity using database-specific tools, including ODBC Driver (Open Database Connectivity Driver) or Access Driver.

Fig 3. Unity Interface for Database Connection

The data link between Unity and Microsoft Access database is implemented using Unity's C# Script.

In Unity, create an object for database connectivity and connect it to a program named ODBC.cs (C# Script)

```

using System.Collections;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using UnityEngine;
using System.Data.Odbc;
using System;

public class ODBC : MonoBehaviour {
    public enum DbType {
        MySQL,
        Access
    }

    public OdbcConnection conn;
    public OdbcCommand cmd = null;
    public DbType DbType;
    public string dbName;
    // use this for initialization
    public object connect (string tagline, int string objName)
    {
        object value;
        OdbcDataAdapter rd;
        cmd.CommandText = string.Format("select tagline,descript from taglist where tag='{0}'",tagline );
        rd = cmd.ExecuteReader ();
        rd.Read ();
        value = rd.GetValue (0);
        objName = rd.GetString (1);
        rd.Close ();
        rd = null;
        return value;
    }

    public object detState (string tagline)
    {
        object value;
        OdbcDataAdapter rd;
        cmd.CommandText = string.Format("select State from State where beision='{0}'",tagline );
        rd = cmd.ExecuteReader ();
        rd.Read ();
        value = rd.GetValue(0);
        rd.Close ();
        rd = null;
        return value;
    }

    public object connect (string tagline)
    {
        object value;
    }
}
    
```

Fig 4. C# Script for connecting Unity and ODBC

Unity and Database Linking program flowchart(Fig.5).

Fig 5. Unity and Database Linking Program Flow

Database design

The database is implemented using Microsoft Access or My SQL.

The database field was set to the unique identifier field, channel name field, device name field, address field, data type field, and numerical field.

Channel	Device	Tag	address	DataType	Enable	Alarm	TagValue	Descript
m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M0	002001	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 배상단추
2 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M1	002002	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1공 PLC자동순전
3 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M2	002003	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1공 송풍기동감시
4 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M3	002004	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1공 송풍기동감시
5 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M4	002005	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 송풍기동부하
6 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M5	002006	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	-1	0	0공 송풍기동부하
7 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M6	002007	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1공 공도감량개
8 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M7	002008	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 공량감량개
9 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M8	002009	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 공도부하
10 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M9	002010	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1건물1_Y기동감시
11 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M10	002011	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0건물1_기동감시
12 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M11	002012	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1건물2_Y기동감시
13 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M12	002013	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0건물2_기동감시
14 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M13	002014	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 송풍기동감시
15 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M14	002015	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 송풍기동감시
16 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M15	002016	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 송풍기동부하
17 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M16	002017	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 송풍기동부하
18 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M17	002018	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 공도감량개
19 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M18	002019	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 공량감량개
20 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M19	002020	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 공도부하
21 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M20	002021	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 배상단추
22 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M21	002022	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 PLC자동순전
23 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M260	002481	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 후진기동감시
24 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M261	002482	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 후진기동감시
25 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M24	002025	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 후진제안발개
26 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M25	002026	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1공 후진제안발개
27 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M26	002027	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 과부하
28 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M27	002028	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2	0	0공 전방자동결합
29 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M28	002029	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2	0	-1공 후방자동결합
30 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M29	002030	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 후방기동신호
31 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M30	002031	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 과부하기동신호
32 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M31	002032	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 전방실속발개
33 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M32	002033	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 전방뒤회발개
34 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M33	002034	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 후방실속발개
35 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M34	002035	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 후방뒤회발개
36 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M35	002036	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	-1공 후방기동신호
37 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M36	002037	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1	0	0공 과부하
38 m_Eth	PLC1	P1-M37	002038	Boolean	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	0	0	0공 과부하신호

Fig 6. Addressed values in Microsoft Access

OPC Server

As OPC Server, we collect data from physical I/O using KEPServer Ex V4.0.

Fig. 5 shows the SCADA design scheme using Unity.

Fig 7. Installing KEPServer Ex V4.0.

Fig 8. Address of process using KEPServer Ex V4.0.

Results and discussion

The evaluation of 3D GUI for SCADA of a Unity-based heat treatment process control system is done by indicating the advantages and disadvantages of users using the previous 2D GUI.

We set up the same task with the same data for 2D GUI and 3D GUI and measure and evaluate the time required to complete the task.

The object is inspected through the monitoring of the condition of the hot wire during the heat treatment process. The hot wire is in the heat treatment furnace and consists of 24 beams.

The process values to be monitored are temperature, voltage, current, frequency, etc.

Since the number of coil bundles of each heating wire is different, the monitoring data values are also individual.

We prepare 10 trained people to compare and evaluate 3D GUI and 2D GUI.

Five of the ten patients were male and five were female.

We choose the task but exclude the special case or the case of an abnormal problem.

The task is to find the maximum and minimum temperature values for 24 heating wires. The temperature range of the heat-treatment furnace is 0 to 580 °C, and when the temperature is above 300 °C, a yellow flame is created, when the temperature is above 500 °C, a black flame is created. The performance of the proposed project is measured and tabulated by measuring the response time of 10 persons.

To ensure the accuracy of the task, the amount of data is tested according to 20, 50, 100, 200 and 300.

The color change of the filament with temperature change in 3D GUI(Fig. 8).

Fig.9. Heating wire visually showing the temperature change in Unity

The evaluation results for the task are as follows(Fig.9).

Fig.10. Evaluation results for the task

Conclusions

Applications that can be imported into Unity's graphics resources, including 3Ds max, are used in SCADA design by creating graphics that are similar to the real ones of complex mechanical equipment.

Simple and approximate designed patterns with the most important actuators can be connected by means of an electronic device installed in the actuators of the real plant and a sensor to address value correspondence by PLC software.

The 3D GUI of SCADA system, written in the Uniy program by OPC, communicates with PLC in real time.

This allows the real-time monitoring and control of large systems that require processing a large amount of information, both visually and stereo-conveniently.

In addition, the addition of information with the expansion of production will not affect the GUI configuration and design of the SCADA system.

This is another advantage of 3D GUI design for SCADA by Unity.

Furthermore, user experiments have shown that overall trends can be effectively recognized in 3D GUI when the amount of information is relatively large or not all information that needs detailed data can be displayed on a single screen with a moderate scale in 2D GUI.

However, the complexity of equipment graphics and real-time processing is highly dependent on computer performance, which is more expensive than 2D GUI, and the effort and time consuming of SCADA design.

The validity of these ideas should also be evaluated.

Data availability

All data used in this study are available with the approval of the authors.

The impact of the research topic

This research topic does not conflict with other published researchers.

Acknowledgement

I would like to thank the State Commission of Science and Technology of the DPRK for giving selfless assistance to our research work.

Reference

VERSION 5.00

Begin VB.Form Form1

BorderStyle = 1 'Fixed Single

Caption = "Form1"

ClientHeight = 1980

ClientLeft = 150

ClientTop = 795

ClientWidth = 3705

Icon = "Form.frx":0000

LinkTopic = "Form1"

MaxButton = 0 'False

MinButton = 0 'False

ScaleHeight = 1980

ScaleWidth = 3705

StartPosition = 3 'Windows Default

Begin VB.CommandButton Command2

Caption = "Contact off"

Height = 375

Left = 2040

TabIndex = 6

Top = 1440

Width = 1455

End

Begin VB.PictureBox pichook

Height = 975

Left = 5760

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ScaleHeight = 915

ScaleWidth = 1515

TabIndex = 5

Top = 0

Width = 1575

End

Begin VB.CommandButton Command1

Caption = "Contact"

Height = 375

Left = 240

TabIndex = 4

Top = 1440

Width = 1455

End

Begin VB.TextBox ProcID

Height = 285

Left = 1440

TabIndex = 3

Text = "2"

Top = 840

Width = 1455

End

Begin VB.TextBox Server

Height = 285

Left = 1440

TabIndex = 0

Text = "192.168.1.3"

Top = 360

Width = 1455

End

Begin VB.Timer Timer1

Enabled = 0 'False

Interval = 1000

Left = 360

Top = 1440

End

Begin VB.Image Img

Height = 240

Index = 0

Left = 4320

Picture = "Form.frx":000C

Top = 1560

Width = 240

End

Begin VB.Image Img

Height = 240

Index = 1

Left = 5040

Picture = "Form.frx":0396

Top = 1560

Width = 240

End

Begin VB.Image Img

Height = 240

Index = 2

Left = 5760

Picture = "Form.frx":0720

Top = 1560

Width = 240

End

Begin VB.Label label2

Caption = "Process number"

Height = 255

Left = 240

TabIndex = 2

Top = 840

Width = 855

End

Begin VB.Label Label1

Caption = "Server address"

Height = 255

Left = 240

TabIndex = 1

Top = 360

Width = 1095

End

Begin VB.Menu mnupopup

Caption = "Menu"

Begin VB.Menu mnuset

Caption = "Setting"

End

Begin VB.Menu mnuexit

Caption = "Finish"

End

End

End

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```
Attribute VB_Name = "Form1"
Attribute VB_GlobalNameSpace = False
Attribute VB_Creatable = False
Attribute VB_PredeclaredId = True
Attribute VB_Exposed = False
Option Explicit
Public Chanel As String
Public Device As String
Dim WithEvents ConnectedGroup As OPCGroup
Attribute ConnectedGroup.VB_VarHelpID = -1
Dim ConnectedOPCServer As OPCServer
Dim ConnectedServerGroup As OPCGroups
Dim OPCItemCollection As OPCItems
Dim ItemServerHandles() As Long
Dim ItemServerErrors() As Long
Dim ItemCount As Long
Dim conn As Connection
Dim conn1 As Connection
Dim rs As Recordset, rs1 As Recordset
Dim rec As Boolean
Dim PC As Boolean
Dim ID As String
Private Declare Function RegCreateKey Lib "advapi32.dll" Alias "RegCreateKeyA" (ByVal hKey As Long,
ByVal lpSubKey As String, phkResult As Long) As Long
Private Declare Function RegCloseKey Lib "advapi32.dll" (ByVal hKey As Long) As Long
Private Declare Function RegSetValueEx Lib "advapi32.dll" Alias "RegSetValueExA" (ByVal hKey As
Long, ByVal lpValueName As String, ByVal Reserved As Long, ByVal dwType As Long, lpData As Any,
ByVal cbData As Long) As Long
Const HKEY_CURRENT_USER = &H80000001
Const HKEY_LOCAL_MACHINE = &H80000002
Private Type NOTIFYICONDATA
    cbSize As Long
    hWnd As Long
    uId As Long
    uFlags As Long
    ucallbackMessage As Long
    hIcon As Long
    szTip As String * 64
End Type
Private Const NIM_ADD = &H0
Private Const NIM_MODIFY = &H1
Private Const NIM_DELETE = &H2
Private Const NIF_MESSAGE = &H1
```



```
Private Const NIF_ICON = &H2
Private Const NIF_TIP = &H4
Private Const WM_LBUTTONDOWNBLCLK = &H203
Private Const WM_LBUTTONDOWN = &H201
Private Const WM_RBUTTONDOWN = &H205
Private Declare Function Shell_NotifyIcon Lib "shell32" Alias "Shell_NotifyIconA" (ByVal dwMessage As Long, pnid As NOTIFYICONDATA) As Boolean
Dim TrayI As NOTIFYICONDATA
Private Sub OPCCConnect()
    Dim OPCItemIDs() As String
    Dim ClientHandles() As Long
    SaveString HKEY_CURRENT_USER, "software\OPCclient", "a", Str(PC)
    conn.Execute "delete * from setValue"
    conn.Execute "Update State set State=0 where Device='c'"
    rs.Open "SELECT * FROM TagList", conn
    rs.MoveFirst
    Do Until rs.EOF
        ItemCount = rs!ID
        rs.MoveNext
    Loop
    ReDim OPCItemIDs(ItemCount) As String
    ReDim ClientHandles(ItemCount) As Long
    rs.MoveFirst
    Do Until rs.EOF
        OPCItemIDs(rs!ID) = rs!channel & "." & rs!Device & "." & rs!address & "@" & rs!DataType
        ClientHandles(rs!ID) = rs!ID
        rs.MoveNext
    Loop
    rs.Close
    Set ConnectedOPCServer = New OPCServer
    ConnectedOPCServer.Connect "KEPware.KEPServerEx.V4"
    Set ConnectedServerGroup = ConnectedOPCServer.OPCGroups
    ConnectedServerGroup.DefaultGroupIsActive = True
    ConnectedServerGroup.DefaultGroupDeadband = 0
    Set ConnectedGroup = ConnectedServerGroup.Add("group1")
    ConnectedGroup.UpdateRate = 1000
    ConnectedGroup.IsSubscribed = True
    Set OPCItemCollection = ConnectedGroup.OPCItems
    OPCItemCollection.DefaultIsActive = True
    OPCItemCollection.AddItem ItemCount, OPCItemIDs, ClientHandles, ItemServerHandles,
    ItemServerErrors
    TrayI.cbSize = Len(TrayI)
    TrayI.hWnd = pichook.hWnd
```


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```
TrayI.uId = 1&
TrayI.uFlags = NIF_ICON Or NIF_TIP Or NIF_MESSAGE
TrayI.ucallbackMessage = WM_LBUTTONDOWN
TrayI.hIcon = Img(0).Picture
Shell_NotifyIcon NIM_ADD, TrayI
Me.Hide
End Sub
Public Sub OPCDisconnect()
Timer1.Enabled = False
conn.Close
Set rs = Nothing
Set conn = Nothing
OPCItemCollection.Remove ItemCount, ItemServerHandles, ItemServerErrors
Set OPCItemCollection = Nothing
ConnectedServerGroup.Remove ("group1")
Set ConnectedServerGroup = Nothing
Set ConnectedGroup = Nothing
ConnectedOPCServer.Disconnect
Set ConnectedOPCServer = Nothing
End Sub
Public Sub OPCItemWrite(ByVal Index As Integer, ByVal Value As Variant)
Dim item As OPCItem
Set item = OPCItemCollection.GetOPCItem(Val(ItemServerHandles(Index)))
item.Write (Val(Value))
End Sub
Public Function OPCItemQuality(ByVal Index As Integer)
Dim item As OPCItem
Set item = OPCItemCollection.GetOPCItem(Val(ItemServerHandles(Index)))
OPCItemQuality = item.Quality
End Function
Private Sub Command1_Click()
On Error GoTo Err_1
Timer1.Enabled = True
rec = False
Set conn = New Connection
Set conn1 = New Connection
Set rs = New Recordset
Set rs1 = New Recordset
'Driver=MySQL ODBC 5.1 Driver;SERVER=127.0.0.1;UID=root;DATABASE=proc2;PORT=3306
conn.Open "Driver=MySQL ODBC 5.1 Driver;SERVER=" & Server.Text &
";UID=root;DATABASE=proc" & ProcID.Text & ";PORT=3306"
OPCConnect
PC = True
```



```
Exit Sub
Err_1:
conn.Open "Driver={Microsoft Access Driver (*.mdb)};dbq=e:/database.mdb"
OPCConnect
PC = False
MsgBox " Access ", vbInformation, "Inform"
End Sub
Private Sub Command2_Click()
OPCDisconnect
End Sub
Sub ConnectedGroup_DataChange(ByVal TransactionID As Long, ByVal NumItems As Long,
ClientHandles() As Long, ItemValues() As Variant, Qualities() As Long, TimeStamps() As Date)
On Error GoTo Err
Dim i As Integer
For i = 1 To NumItems
Dim state As Boolean
state = False
If Qualities(i) = &HC0 Then state = True
conn.Execute "update TagList set tagValue=" & CCur(ItemValues(i)) & ",Enable=" & state & " where
id=" & ClientHandles(i)
If rs.state = ObjectStateEnum.adStateOpen Then rs.Close
rs.Open "select alarm,device from taglist where id=" & ClientHandles(i), conn
If CBool(rs!alarm) And CBool(ItemValues(i) And Val(rs!alarm) <> 3) Then
conn.Execute "insert into alarm (id,device,alarm,saved) values (" & ClientHandles(i) & "," &
rs!Device & "," & rs!alarm & ",now())"
End If
rs.Close
Next
Exit Sub
Err:
OPCDisconnect
Command1_Click
End Sub
Private Sub mnuset_Click()
Me.Show
End Sub
Private Sub Timer1_Timer()
Dim rs As Recordset, rs1 As Recordset
Set rs = New Recordset
Set rs1 = New Recordset
rs.Open "select * from setValue", con
If rs.EOF = False Then
rs.MoveFirst
```



```
rs1.Open "select id from Taglist where tag='" & rs!Tag & "'", conn
OPCItemWrite Int(rs1!ID), rs!m_value
rs1.Close
conn.Execute "delete * from setValue where ID='" & rs!ID
End If
rs.Close
conn.Execute "Update State set State='" & PC & " where Device='c'"
conn.Execute "Update State set State='" & OPCItemQuality(1) & " where Device='plc3'"
conn.Execute "Update State set State='" & OPCItemQuality(138) & " where Device='plc4'"
conn.Execute "Update State set State='" & OPCItemQuality(189) & " where Device='plc5'"
Dim n As Integer
Dim fld As Field
Dim tags As String
Dim values As String
n = n + 1
If n = 60 Then
rs.Open "SELECT * FROM hist", conn
rs.MoveFirst
For Each fld In rs.Fields
If fld.Name <> "Saved" Then
rs1.Open "SELECT id FROM TagList where tag='" & fld.Name & "'", conn
Print rs1!ID
If OPCItemCollection.item(Int(rs1!ID)).Quality Then
tags = tags & fld.Name & ","
values = values & OPCItemCollection.item(Int(rs1!ID)).Value & ","
End If
rs1.Close
End If
Next
conn.Execute "insert into hist (" & tags & "Saved) values (" & values & "Now())"
n = 0
End If

If PC Then
Static Tek As Integer
TrayI.hIcon = Img(Tek).Picture
Tek = Tek + 1
If Tek = 3 Then Tek = 1
Shell_NotifyIcon NIM_MODIFY, TrayI
TrayI.szTip = "Contact on" & Chr(0)
Else
TrayI.hIcon = Img(0).Picture
Shell_NotifyIcon NIM_MODIFY, TrayI
```



```
TrayI.szTip = "Contact off" & Chr(0)
End If
Set rs = Nothing
Set rs1 = Nothing

End Sub

Private Sub Form_Unload(Cancel As Integer)
OPCDisconnect
TrayI.cbSize = Len(TrayI)
TrayI.hWnd = pichook.hWnd
TrayI.uId = 1&
Shell_NotifyIcon NIM_DELETE, TrayI
End
End Sub

Sub SaveString(hKey As Long, strPath As String, strValue As String, strData As String)
Dim Ret
RegCreateKey hKey, strPath, Ret
RegSetValueEx Ret, strValue, 0, 1, ByVal strData, Len(strData)
RegCloseKey Ret
End Sub

Private Sub mnuexit_Click()
Unload Me
End Sub

Private Sub pichook_MouseDown(Button As Integer, Shift As Integer, X As Single, Y As Single)
Dim msg
msg = X / Screen.TwipsPerPixelX
If msg = WM_LBUTTONDOWN Then mnupopup.Visible = False
If msg = WM_RBUTTONDOWN Then Me.PopupMenu mnupopup
End Sub
```

